

CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF LEPIDOPTERA OF ČELAREVO (VOJVODINA, SERBIA)

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Abstract

Moths were collected in Čelarevo (UTM CR81) from 2008 to 2014 by light traps, type RO Agrobecej, with a 250-W mercury lamp; 234,000 specimens were collected of which 223,226 were determined. A total of 292 moth species belonged to the following families: Psychidae 1, Tortricidae 2, Cossidae 4, Limacodidae 1, Crambidae 3, Drepanidae 4, Lasiocampidae 7, Saturniidae 1, Sphingidae 13, Geometridae 55, Notodontidae 14, Erebidae 44 (subfamilies Lymantriinae 7, Arctiinae 15, Herminiinae 2, Hypeninae 2, Rivulinae 1, Scoliopteryginae 1, Calpinae 1, Aveniinae 1, Eublemminae 2, Phytometrinae 1, Erebiniae 11), Nolidae 6 and Noctuidae 137. In this paper, data are given for some 194,305 specimens of 155 species (excluding Noctuidae). The finding of *Stegania cararia*, *Cyclophora pendularia*, *Scopula flaccidaria*, *Rhyparioides metelkana* and *Arytrura musculus* was significant.

KEY WORDS: Lepidoptera, fauna, *Arytrura musculus*, *Rhyparioides metelkana*

Introduction

Previous data on Lepidoptera in Čelarevo included 39 species (Vajgand *et al.*, 2009, Vajgand, 2009, 2010a, 2010b, 2010c, 2010d, 2012a, 2012b). Most of them related to species with impact on agriculture production, rare and other interesting species. From this region, data on moths are available for Fruška Gora (Stojanović *et al.* 2010, Stojanović, 2012), Novi Sad (Kereši & Almaši, 2009) and Sombor (Vajgand 1988, Vajgand, 1995a, Vajgand, 1995b, Vajgand 1995c, Vajgand 1996, Vajgand 1999, Jakšić & Dimović, 2000, Vajgand 2001, Vajgand 2003, Stojanović & Vajgand 2007, Stojanović *et al* 2006, Vajgand 2009, Vajgand 2010a, Vajgand 2010c, Vajgand 2011, Vajgand 2012a).

A light trap was placed to establish the frequency of the appearance of moths that significantly affect agriculture. Since no selective attractant was used, many photophilous insects were collected. Only data on moths are presented here.

Methods

Research was carried out between 2008 and 2014 with a light trap situated a few kilometers north of the village of Čelarevo, UTM code CR81.

Čelarevo is situated on the left bank of the River Danube. The light trap was in an experimental field of the Agrimatco company. Nearby is 0.5 ha of apple orchards, surrounded by a 2-km circle of agrobiocenosis, the dominant crops being corn, wheat, soybean and sugar beet. The dominant soil type is a degraded chernozem-like meadow. Further towards the south is a wetland area, one kilometer wide. This area is partly flooded when the level of the Danube is high. In this area, poplars (*Populus* spp.) and other marshy trees (*Salix* spp., *Quercus* spp...), shrubbery (*Prunus spinosa*, *Crataegus* spp.) and herbaceous plants (*Phragmites* spp., *Typha* spp...) are predominant.

The light trap was of the type RO Agrobečej. The source of light used was a 250-W mercury lamp. The trap was attended from the beginning of April until mid-October. Specimens were killed with an insecticide based on dichlorvos and were collected every day. They were separately packed and sent to the laboratory for determination.

Determination of moths was made using the following keys: Abafi (1907), Forster & Wohlfahrt (1980, 1981, 1984), Freina & Witt (1987) and Rakosy (1996).

Certain specimens were protected by standard procedure and are kept in the author's collection. Taxonomy follows Karsholt *et al.* (2013), and species codes from Karsholt & Razowski (1996) are included in the species list. Faunal types are based on Varga (1977) and Varga & Gyulai (1978). The order of family and species follows Fauna Europaea (Karsholt & Nieukerken, 2013).

Type of migrators follows the classification of Eitschberger *et al.* (1991).

Results

List of the species recorded in Čelarevo between 2008 and 2014. Species ordinal number is followed by the species code number as proposed by Karsholt and Razowski (1996).

1. 961 *Canephora unicolor* (Poda, 1761)

Date of collection: 25.05.2009. One moth collected.

Faunal type: undefined.

2. 4370 *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus, 1758

Date of collection: four moths 25.05.2012. (2 ex.), 19.05.2013, 28.05.2013.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

3. 5144 *Cydia pomonella* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: six moths 19.08.2008, 15.08.2009, 30.08.2011, 14.04.2012, 18.08.2013, 14.08.2014.

Faunal type: Holopalaeartic.

4. 4151 *Cossus cossus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 13.05.-16.08. (Appendix Table A-I).

Faunal type: Holopalaeartic.

5. 4166 *Dyspessa ulula* (Borkhausen, 1790)

Date of collection: 23.04.2009, 16.05.2009, 18.05.2009, 19.05.2009, 03.05.2013, 26.05.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

6. 4176 *Zeuzera pyrina* (Linnaeus, 1761)

Date of collection: 03.06.-16.08. (Appendix Table A-II).

Faunal type: Holopalaeartic.

7. 4178 *Phragmataecia castaneae* (Hübner, 1790)

Date of collection: 21.04.-03.09. (Appendix Table A-III).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

8. 3907 *Apoda limacodes* (Hufnagel, 1766)

Date of collection: 11.06.2008, 23.06.2008, 01.06.2012, 01.07.2012, 01.08.2013, 24.06.2014, 03.07.2014.
Seven moths collected.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

9. 6577 *Loxostege sticticalis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 01.05.-02.10. (Appendix Table A-IV).

Faunal type: Holarctic

10. 6649 *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796)

Date of collection: (Appendix Table A-V).

Faunal type: Holarctic

11. * *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859)

* Species code number is not available according to Karsholt & Razowski (1996)

Date of collection: 19.10.2014.

Faunal type: undefined.

12. 7503 *Watsonalla binaria* (Hufnagel, 1767)

Date of collection: 20.06.2008, 04.08.2008, 17.08.2008, 17.06.2011, 30.07.2011, 07.08.2012, 26.08.2012, 13.09.2012 and 28.08.2013. Nine moths collected.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic

13. 7512 *Cilix glaucata* (Scopoli, 1763)

Date of collection: 23.06.2008, 29.08.2008, 05.09.2008, 11.09.2008, 12.09.2008, 20.09.2008, 06.09.2011, 08.09.2011, 10.09.2011 and 27.04.2012. Ten moths collected.

Faunal type: Holarctic.

14. 7481 *Thyatira batis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 24.4-20.09. (Appendix Table A-VI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

15. 7483 *Habrosyne pyritoides* (Hufnagel, 1766)

Date of collection: 2.05.-26.08. (Appendix Table A-VII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

16. 6743 *Malacosoma neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 08.06.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

17. 6749 *Lasiocampa trifolii* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 23.08.2009.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

18. 6753 *Lasiocampa quercus* (Linnaeus, 1761)

Date of collection: 03.08.-02.09. (Appendix Table A-VIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

19. 6755 *Macrothylacia rubi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 11.05.2009 and 20.05.2009.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

20. 6730 *Trichiura crataegi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 22.06.2012, 24.06.2012, 05.07.2012, 07.07.2012 (2 ex.) and 08.07.2012. Six moths collected.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

21. 6777 *Gastropacha quercifolia* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 18.05.-22.09. (Appendix Table A-IX).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

22. 6780 *Odonestis pruni* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 17.05.-15.08. (Appendix Table A-X).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

23. 6794 *Saturnia pavonia* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 09.04.2009, 10.04.2010, 18.04.2010, 07.04.2011, 08.04.2011, 09.04.2011 (2 ex.), 18.04.2011, 19.04.2011, 23.04.2011 and 29.04.2013. Fifteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic

24. 6819 *Mimas tiliae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 19.04.-19.08. (Appendix Table A-XI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

25. 6822 *Smerinthus ocellata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 18.04.-28.08. (Appendix Table A-XII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

26. 6824 *Laothoe populi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 25.04.-05.09. (Appendix Table A-XIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

27. 6828 *Agrilus convolvuli* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 10.06.-04.10. (Appendix Table A-XIV).

Faunal type: Paleotropical-subtropical.

28. 6830 *Acherontia atropos* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 14.09.2010 (2 ex.) and 28.09.2014.

Faunal type: Paleotropical-subtropical.

29. 6832 *Sphinx ligustri* Linnaeus, 1758

Date of collection: 02.06.2008, 24.07.2010, 01.08.2010, 03.07.2011, 25.07.2011, 08.07.2012 and 14.07.2012. Seven moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

30. 6843 *Macroglossum stellatarum* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 27.08.2008, 09.06.2009, 06.08.2010, 15.04.2013, 30.07.2013 and 24.08.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

31. 6849 *Proserpinus proserpina* (Pallas, 1772)

Date of collection: 22.04.2008, 12.05.2008, 02.06.2008, 17.05.2009, 18.04.2010, 19.04.2010, 25.04.2010, 12.05.2010, 28.05.2010, 17.06.2010, 17.04.2011, 22.04.2011 (2 ex.), 23.04.2011 (4 ex.), 25.04.2011, 08.06.2011, 23.06.2011 and 27.04.2013. Twenty-one moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

32. 6853 *Hyles euphorbiae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 13.07.2008 (2 ex.), 16.07.2008, 19.06.2009, 14.07.2009, 18.07.2009, 20.07.2009, 23.07.2009, 15.08.2009, 19.08.2009, 12.05.2010, 16.06.2010, 18.07.2010, 21.07.2011, 06.08.2010, 10.08.2010, 19.08.2010 (2 ex.), 09.09.2010, 20.05.2011, 05.06.2011, 27.07.2011, 26.07.2012, 08.08.2012, 10.05.2013, 06.07.2013, 29.07.2013 and 04.09.2014. Twenty-eight moths collected.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

33. 6855 *Hyles galii* (Rottemburg, 1775)

Date of collection: 11.08.2010, 16.09.2010 and 19.05.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

34. 6860 *Hyles livornica* (Esper, 1779)

Date of collection: 16.06.2008, 13.05.2009, 15.05.2009 (2 ex.), 16.05.2009 (7 ex.), 17.05.2009 (4 ex.), 19.05.2009 (5 ex.), 24.05.2009, 25.05.2009 (4 ex.), 26.05.2009 (2 ex.), 27.05.2009 (4 ex.), 09.06.2009, 25.07.2009, 01.08.2009, 30.05.2013 and 23.05.2014. Thirty-six moths collected.

Faunal type: Paleotropical-subtropical.

35. 6862 *Deilephila elpenor* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 07.05.-20.08. (Appendix Table A-XV).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

36. 6863 *Deilephila porcellus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 01.07.2008, 20.07.2008, 21.07.2008, 29.07.2008 (2 ex.), 06.08.2008, 16.07.2009, 18.07.2009, 03.08.2009, 02.05.2010, 05.05.2010, 09.06.2010, 13.07.2010, 15.07.2010, 18.07.2010, 03.08.2010, 15.08.2010, 14.05.2011, 20.05.2011, 11.06.2011, 23.06.2011 and 08.08.2011. Twenty-two moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

37. 7524 *Abraxas sylvata* (Scopoli, 1763)

Date of collection: 22.07.2011.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

38. 7530 *Ligdia adustata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 01.06.2008, 13.08.2008, 14.08.2008 (2 ex.), 15.08.2008, 17.08.2008, 18.08.2008, 22.08.2008, 27.08.2009, 19.08.2010, 22.04.2011, 30.04.2013, 04.05.2013, 06.05.2013, 13.07.2013, 22.07.2014 and 23.08.2014. Seventeen moths collected. Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

39. 7665 *Angerona prunaria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 06.08.2008, 13.05.2009, 15.06.2010, 21.05.2011, 01.06.2011, 06.06.2011, 10.08.2011, 13.08.2011, 24.08.2011, 21.05.2012 and 28.07.2012. Eleven moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

40. 7829 *Lomographa temerata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 10.07.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

41. 7674 *Lycia hirtaria* (Clerck, 1758)

Date of collection: 08.04.2010.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

42. 7699 *Erannis defoliaria* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 01.10.2014.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

43. 7794 *Ascotis selenaria* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 09.4-09.09. (Appendix Table A-XVI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

44. 7804 *Ematurga atomaria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 25.04.-05.09. (Appendix Table A-XVII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

45. 7527 *Lomaspilis marginata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 14.04.-27.08. (Appendix Table A-XVIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

46. 7532 *Stegania cararia* (Hübner, 1790)

Date of collection: 23.08.2009, 03.09.2009, 12.09.2009, 14.09.2009, 18.09.2009 (2 ex.), 22.09.2009, 22.07.2011 and 03.08.2011. Nine moths collected.

Faunal type: European-eastern Asian disjunct.

47. 7534 *Stegania dilectaria* (Hübner, 1790)

Date of collection: 19.07.2008, 28.08.2008 and 22.04.2014.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

48. 7663 *Colotois pennaria* (Linnaeus, 1761)

Date of collection: 03.10.2010.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

49. 7632 *Ennomos autumnaria* (Werneburg, 1859)

Date of collection: 20.06.2012.

Faunal type: Circumboreal, Holarctic.

50. 7641 *Selenia dentaria* (Fabricius, 1775)

Date of collection: 16.06.2010 and 17.06.2010.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

51. 7642 *Selenia lunularia* (Hübner, 1788)

Date of collection: 27.06.2008, 17.07.2008, 20.07.2008, 21.07.2008, 16.04.2009, 20.04.2009, 19.07.2009, 08.08.2009, 23.04.2011, 26.04.2011, 21.06.2011, 30.06.2011, 16.06.2012, 18.06.2012, 22.06.2012, 28.08.2013, 29.04.2014, 28.06.2014, 21.08.2014, 24.08.2014, 04.09.2014 (2 ex.), 05.09.2014 (2 ex.), 12.09.2014 (2 ex.) and 20.09.2014. Twenty-seven moths collected.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

52. 7613 *Opisthograptis luteolata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 22.08.2008, 05.05.2010, 03.08.2011, 02.05.2012 (2 ex.), 25.04.2013 and 29.04.2013.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

53. 7615 *Epione repandaria* (Hufnagel, 1767)

Date of collection: 23.07.2011, 07.07.2012 and 13.07.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

54. 7618 *Therapis flavicaria* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 04.05.2010.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

55. 7654 *Crocalis elinguaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 06.07.2010 and 13.07.2010.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

56. 7606 *Plagodis pulveraria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 19.07.2008, 18.07.2011 (2 ex.), 19.07.2011 and 30.04.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

57. 7607 *Plagodis dolabraria* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Date of collection: 30.06.2011 and 20.07.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

58. 7540 *Macaria alternata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 12.04.-13.09. (Appendix Table A-XIX).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

59. 7542 *Macaria liturata* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 08.07.2010 and 04.06.2011.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

60. 7547 *Chiasmia clathrata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 21.04.-16.09. (Appendix Table A-XX).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

61. 7571 *Isturgia arenacearia* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 13.04.-24.09. (Appendix Table A-XXI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

62. 7975 *Thetidia smaragdaria* (Fabricius, 1787)

Date of collection: 05.08.2008, 07.08.2008, 21.08.2009, 13.06.2011, 27.05.2012 and 19.08.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

63. 8663 *Minoa murinata* (Scopoli, 1763)

Date of collection: 07.06.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

64. 8638 *Lithostege griseata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 09.05.2008, 11.04.2009, 17.04.2009, 09.05.2009 (2 ex.), 18.05.2009, 31.05.2009, 09.06.2009, 21.04.2010, 24.04.2010 (5 ex.), 25.04.2010 (2 ex.), 26.04.2010 (2 ex.), 30.04.2010 (2 ex.), 05.05.2010, 22.04.2011, 24.04.2011, 18.05.2011, 16.05.2013 and 29.05.2013. Twenty-six moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

65. 8639 *Lithostege farinata* (Hufnagel, 1767)

Date of collection: 22.04.-03.06. (Appendix Table A-XXII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

66. 8319 *Cosmorhoe ocellata* (Linnaeus 1758)

Date of collection: 24.08.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

67. 8335 *Eulithis pyraliata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 09.06.2009, 12.06.2011, 22.06.2011, 07.06.2012, 08.06.2012, 11.06.2012 and 03.06.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

68. 8385 *Colostygia pectinataria* (Knoch, 1781)

Date of collection: 25.05.2011.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

69. 8483 *Eupithecia linariata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 10.07.2008, 11.07.2008, 17.07.2008, 19.07.2008 and 29.07.2011.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

70. 8509 *Eupithecia centaureata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 29.06.2008, 04.07.2008 (2 ex.), 12.08.2008, 27.08.2008, 18.06.2009, 17.08.2009, 20.05.2011, 22.05.2011, 23.06.2011, 21.05.2012, 24.06.2012, 08.09.2013, 10.05.2014, 21.07.2014, 22.07.2014 and 05.09.2014. Seventeen moths collected. Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

71. 8601 *Chloroclystis v-ata* (Haworth, 1809)

Date of collection: 04.06.2008 (2 ex.), 10.04.2009, 10.06.2009 and 21.06.2011.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

72. 8314 *Pelurga comitata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 13.08.2008, 14.08.2008 (2 ex.), 15.08.2008 and 11.09.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

73. 8221 *Lythria purpuraria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 23.08.2008, 25.05.2009, 30.05.2009, 19.08.2009 (2 ex.), 24.06.2012, 14.07.2012, 24.07.2012, 25.07.2012, 28.07.2012 (4 ex.), 05.08.2012, 06.08.2012, 10.08.2012 (2 ex.), 19.08.2012, 04.08.2013 and 01.09.2013. Twenty moths collected.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

74. 8246 *Orthonama obstipata* (Fabricius, 1794)

Date of collection: 10.07.2008, 03.10.2008, 11.10.2008, 12.10.2008, 13.10.2008, 21.07.2009, 18.09.2009, 12.10.2010 (2 ex.), 23.07.2011, 09.10.2013, 14.10.2013, 09.07.2014 and 28.09.2014. Fourteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Subtropical.

75. 8253 *Xanthorhoe ferrugata* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 10.05.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

76. 8268 *Catarhoe rubidata* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 18.05.2009, 24.06.2009, 26.05.2010, 18.05.2011, 20.05.2011, 22.05.2011 and 08.08.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

77. 8287 *Costaconvexa polygrammata* (Borkhausen, 1794)

Date of collection: 25.04.-07.10. (Appendix Table A-XXIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

78. 8289 *Campogramma bilineata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 28.06.2010.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

79. 8012 *Cyclophora pendularia* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 10.06.2009.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

80. 8014 *Cyclophora annularia* (Fabricius 1775)

Date of collection: 12.05.2009, 01.06.2011, 23.06.2011, 05.07.2011, 23.08.2011, 24.08.2011, 25.08.2011, 26.08.2011 (2 ex.) and 28.08.2011. Ten moths collected.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

81. 8022 *Cyclophora punctaria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 01.05.2011, 22.05.2011, 25.05.2011 and 13.07.2011.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

82. 8104 *Idaea muricata* (Hufnagel, 1767)

Date of collection: 23.05.-29.09. (Appendix Table A-XXIV).

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

83. 8184 *Idaea aversata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 16.05.-30.09. (Appendix Table A-XXV).

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

84. 8186 *Idaea degeneraria* (Hübner, 1799)

Date of collection: 01.05.2009, 21.08.2010, 02.08.2011, 27.09.2012, 04.05.2013, 05.05.2013 and 11.05.2013.

Faunal type: Ponto-Mediterranean.

85. 8211 *Rhodometra sacraria* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Date of collection: 19.08.2008 (2 ex.), 28.08.2008, 30.08.2008, 08.09.2008 (2 ex.), 09.09.2008, 11.09.2008, 03.10.2008, 08.10.2008, 14.10.2008, 15.10.2008, 17.08.2008, 14.09.2009, 24.09.2009, 29.09.2011, 05.09.2012, 09.10.2013 and 19.08.2014. Nineteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Subtropical

86. 8205 *Rhodostrophia vibicaria* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 09.05.-02.10 (Appendix Table A-XXVI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

87. 8036 *Scopula immorata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 04.07.2008, 12.07.2008, 11.09.2008, 30.06.2009, 06.07.2009, 14.07.2009, 29.07.2009, 18.08.2010, 20.08.2010, 09.09.2010, 10.09.2011, 08.06.2012, 01.06.2013 and 26.07.2013.

Fourteen moths collected. Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

88. 8045 *Scopula ornata* (Scopoli, 1763)

Date of collection: 28.08.2008, 03.10.2008, 17.05.2009, 30.09.2009, 25.09.2012 and 10.07.2013.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

89. 8054 *Scopula rubiginata* (Hufnagel, 1767)

Date of collection: 05.09.2014 and 12.09.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

90. 8068 *Scopula flaccidaria* (Zeller, 1852)

Date of collection: 12.08.2008 and 19.09.2012.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

91. 8027 *Timandra comae* Schmidt, 1931

Date of collection: 14.04.-09.10 (Appendix Table A-XXVII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

92. 8698 *Clostera curtula* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 08.04.-20.8 (Appendix Table A-XXVIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

93. 8699 *Clostera pigra* (Hufnagel, 1766)

Date of collection: 16.08.2008, 17.08.2008, 20.08.2008 (2 ex.), 15.08.2009, 22.08.2009, 24.08.2009, 25.08.2009, 26.04.2010, 26.05.2010, 16.06.2010, 03.08.2010, 05.08.2010, 09.08.2010, 22.08.2010, 23.08.2010, 27.08.2010 (2 ex.), 23.04.2011, 18.07.2011, 19.08.2011, 21.08.2011 and 09.06.2013. Twenty-three moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

94. 8700 *Clostera anachoreta* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 19.05.-05.09. (Appendix Table A-XXIX).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

95. 8718 *Notodonta tritophus* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 22.05.2012 and 20.06.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

96. 8719 *Notodonta ziczac* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 04.06.2008, 27.06.2008, 03.07.2008, 29.04.2009 (2 ex.), 09.08.2009, 21.08.2009, 25.08.2009, 11.06.2010, 01.07.2010, 18.08.2010, 19.05.2011, 21.05.2011, 09.07.2011, 18.08.2011, 26.08.2011, 04.05.2012 and 22.05.2012. Eighteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

97. 8727 *Pheosia tremula* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 14.04.-10.09. (Appendix Table A-XXX).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

98. 8732 *Pterostoma palpina* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 13.04.-12.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

99. 8747 *Gluphisia crenata* (Esper, 1785)

Date of collection: 03.05.-18.07. (Appendix Table A-XXXII).

Faunal type: Extra-Mediterranean-(Central) European.

100. 8706 *Cerura erminea* (Esper, 1783)

Date of collection: 16.07.2012 and 22.07.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

101. 8710 *Furcula bifida* (Brahm, 1787)

Date of collection: 14.04.2008, 15.08.2008, 01.06.2011, 10.04.2010, 16.06.2012 and 06.09.2013.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

102. 8714 *Dicranura ulmi* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 24.04.2011, 19.04.2013 and 02.05.2013.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

103. 8758 *Stauropus fagi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 10.04.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

104. 8760 *Hybocampa milhauseri* (Fabricius, 1775)

Date of collection: 13.07.2010.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

105. 8762 *Spatalia argentina* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 24.08.2008, 25.08.2009, 06.05.2013 and 08.05.2013.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

106. 10376 *Lymantria dispar* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 08.08.2008, 20.07.2009, 16.07.2010, 15.06.1012, 19.06.2012, 20.06.2012, 21.06.2012 (twenty-four ex.), 22.06.2012 (9 ex.), 12.07.2012, 19.08.2012, 21.06.2013, 12.07.2013, 18.07.2013 and 07.08.2014. Forty-five moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

107. 10387 *Calliteara pudibunda* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 11.05.2009, 10.05.2011, 28.04.2012 and 03.05.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

108. 10410 *Laelia coenosa* (Hübner, 1808)

Date of collection: 11.06.2010, 17.06.2011, 19.06.2011 (2 ex.), 22.06.2011, 23.06.2011, 24.06.2011, 03.09.2011, 15.06.2012, 24.06.2012 and 26.06.2012. Eleven moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

109. 10397 *Orgyia antiqua* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 20.07.2008, 05.08.2008 (2 ex.), 06.08.2008 (4 ex.), 14.08.2008 (2 ex.), 15.08.2008 (5 ex.), 17.08.2008, 06.09.2008, 07.09.2008, 26.06.2009, 24.07.2009, 13.08.2009, 02.09.2009, 03.09.2009, 10.06.2010, 11.06.2010, 25.07.2010, 19.08.2010, 24.08.2010, 27.08.2010, 09.07.2011, 02.07.2012 and 29.07.2013. Thirty-three samples collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

110. 10414 *Leucoma salicis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 02.06.2008, 13.06.2008, 11.08.2008 (2 ex.), 13.08.2008, 21.08.2008, 22.08.2008 (2 ex.), 27.08.2008 (2 ex.), 02.09.2008, 03.09.2008, 05.09.2008 (2 ex.), 06.09.2008, 15.06.2009 (2 ex.), 28.06.2009, 16.08.2009, 25.08.2009, 09.09.2009, 12.06.2010, 14.06.2010, 18.08.2010, 15.07.2011, 15.09.2011 and 26.06.2013. Twenty-seven moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

111. 10405 *Euproctis chrysorrhoea* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 18.08.2009, 22.06.2011, 10.06.2012, 11.06.2012 (12), 15.06.2012 (4 ex.), 14.06.2013, 16.06.2013, 21.06.2013 (6 ex.), 22.06.2013 (4 ex.), 23.06.2013, 28.06.2013, 03.09.2013, 04.09.2013, 06.09.2013, 15.06.2014 (3 ex.), 16.06.2014, 17.06.2014 and 20.06.2014. Thirty-seven moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

112. 10406 *Euproctis similis* (Fuessly, 1775)

Date of collection: 07.08.2013.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

113. 10466 *Thumatha senex* (Hübner, 1808)

Date of collection: 31.05.2008, 11.06.2008, 10.06.2009, 20.08.2009, 24.08.2009, 26.08.2009, 24.06.2012, 10.08.2012 and 08.06.2014. Nine moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

114. 10475 *Miltochrista miniata* (Forster, 1771)

Date of collection: 28.05.2008, 11.06.2008, 12.06.2008, 28.06.2009, 15.07.2009, 14.06.2010, 18.08.2010, 17.09.2010, 05.06.2011, 22.06.2011, 05.07.2011, 09.07.2011, 14.07.2011 and 15.07.2011. Fourteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

115. 10479 *Pelosia muscerda* (Hufnagel, 1766)

Date of collection: 24.05.-19.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

116. 10480 *Pelosia obtusa* (Herr.-Schäff., 1847)

Date of collection: 22.05.-23.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXIV).

Faunal type: European-eastern Asian disjunct.

117. 10485 *Lithosia quadra* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 02.06.-14.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXV).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

118. 10493 *Eilema caniola* (Hübner, 1808)

Date of collection: 09.09.2010.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

119. 10521 *Dysauxes ancilla* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Date of collection: 07.07.2013.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

120. 10550 *Phragmatobia fuliginosa* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 16.04.-30.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXVI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

121. 10566 *Spilosoma lutea* (Hufnagel, 1766)

Date of collection: 29.04.-01.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXVII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

122. 10567 *Spilosoma lubricipeda* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 18.04.-05.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXVIII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

123. 10568 *Spilosoma urticae* (Esper, 1789)

Date of collection: 02.05.2008, 09.05.2008, 10.05.2008, 15.05.2008, 26.05.2008, 28.08.2008, 30.07.2008, 03.08.2008, 12.05.2009, 18.05.2009, 18.07.2009, 06.05.2011, 14.05.2011, 21.05.2011, 06.05.2012, 11.05.2012 and 20.05.2012. Seventeen moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

124. 10570 *Hyphantria cunea* (Drury, 1773)

Date of collection: 03.05.-21.09. (Appendix Table A-XXXIX).

Faunal type: Nearctic.

125. 10572 *Diaphora mendica* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 14.04.2008, 11.04.2009, 16.04.2009, 24.04.2009, 25.04.2009 (3 ex.), 26.04.2009 (3 ex.), 15.04.2010, 18.04.2010 (2 ex.), 29.04.2010, 23.04.2011, 27.04.2011, 28.04.2011, 05.05.2011, 21.04.2012, 27.04.2012, 17.04.2013, 26.04.2013, 27.04.2013, 30.04.2013, 08.04.2014 and 15.04.2014. Twenty-six moths registered.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

126. 10581 *Rhyparioides metelkana* (Lederer, 1861)

Date of collection: 15.07.2011.

Faunal type: European-eastern Asian disjunct.

127. 10583 *Diacrisia sannio* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 03.08.2009, 27.05.2010, 24.06.2010 and 19.08.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

128. 8839 *Paracolax tristalis* (Fabricius, 1794)

Date of collection: 11.09.2009, 10.09.2010, 18.06.2011, 14.06.2012, 20.06.2012 and 21.06.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

129. 8846 *Herminia grisealis* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 14.08.2008, 22.05.2011, 29.05.2011, 04.07.2011, 06.07.2011, 04.08.2011 and 10.08.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

130. 8994 *Hypena proboscidalis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 11.05.-20.09. (Appendix Table A-XL).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

131. 8995 *Hypena rostralis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Collection data: 30.06.2008, 09.08.2008, 11.04.2009, 12.04.2009 (3 ex.), 13.04.2009, 14.04.2009, 15.04.2009, 17.04.2009 (3 ex.), 20.04.2009, 22.04.2009, 24.04.2010 (2 ex.), 06.07.2011, 26.04.2013, 28.04.2013, 30.04.2013, 14.07.2013 and 26.05.2014. Twenty-two moths collected.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

132. 9008 *Rivula sericealis* (Scopoli, 1763)

Date of collection: 15.05.-30.09. (Appendix Table A-XLI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

133. 8985 *Scoliopteryx libatrix* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 19.06.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

134. 8986 *Calyptra thalictri* (Borkhausen, 1790)

Date of collection: 25.06.2008, 20.06.2009, 10.08.2010, 27.08.2010 (2 ex.), 09.09.2010, 13.06.2011, 08.07.2011 and 06.06.2012. Nine moths registered.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

135. 8975 *Laspeyria flexula* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 16.06.2008, 22.06.2008, 29.07.2008, 20.08.2008, 22.08.2008, 23.05.2009, 31.05.2009, 06.06.2009, 08.06.2009, 09.08.2010., 19.08.2010, 25.05.2011 and 23.06.2012. Thirteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

136. 9147 *Eublemma purpurina* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Collection data: 17.07.2008, 22.07.2008 (2 ex.), 07.08.2008, 15.08.2008, 16.10.2008, 20.07.2009, 27.07.2009, 09.09.2009, 04.06.2010, 28.07.2010, 30.07.2010, 06.08.2010, 10.08.2010, 11.05.2012, 08.06.2012, 22.09.2012, 24.09.2012, 07.06.2013, 11.06.2013 (2 ex.), 16.06.2013, 09.08.2013, 14.08.2013, 14.09.2013, 26.09.2013, 14.09.2014 and 01.10.2014. Twenty-nine moths collected.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

137. 9006 *Phytometra viridaria* (Clerck, 1759)

Date of collection: 24.05.2011.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

138. 9018 *Colobochyla salicalis* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 03.05.-03.09. (Appendix A-Table XLII).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

139. 8981 *Arytrura musculus* (Ménétriés, 1859)

Date of collection: 28.06.2008 and 07.07.2009.

Faunal type: Manchurian-(southern Siberian)-Ponto-Pannonian disjunct.

140. 8969 *Euclidia glyphica* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 28.07.2008, 15.08.2008, 16.08.2008, 17.08.2008, 28.08.2010 and 14.07.2011.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

141. 8897 *Minucia lunaris* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 19.05.2014 and 20.05.2014.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

142. 8904 *Dysgonia algira* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Date of collection: 22.05.-20.09. (Appendix Table A-XLIII).

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

143. 8909 *Grammodes stolidia* (Fabricius, 1775)

Date of collection: 05.08.2008, 07.08.2008, 13.08.2008, 15.08.2008, 09.09.2008, 28.06.2009, 04.09.2009, 06.09.2009, 12.09.2009, 14.09.2009, 20.09.2009, 03.10.2009, 17.09.2011, 18.09.2012, 19.09.2012 and 06.09.2014. Sixteen moths collected.

Faunal type: Paletropical.

144. 8874 *Catocala nupta* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Date of collection: 28.06.2009, 25.09.2011, 01.09.2012, 04.09.2012, 02.09.2013, 05.09.2013, 09.10.2013 and 02.10.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

145. 8877 *Catocala elocata* (Esper, 1787)

Date of collection: 19.08.2012, 25.08.2012, 19.09.2012 and 06.09.2014.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

146. 8882 *Catocala promissa* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 28.06.2009.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

147. 8883 *Catocala electa* (Vieweg, 1790)

Date of collection: 19.06.2011, 03.08.2011 and 28.06.2013.

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

148. 8889 *Catocala hymenaea* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

Date of collection: 07.08.2012 and 25.08.2013.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

149. 8890 *Catocala fulminea* (Scopoli, 1763)

Date of collection: 29.06.2009, 24.06.2012, 25.06.2012 and 30.06.2012.

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

150. 10437 *Nola chlamitulalis* (Hübner, 1790)

Date of collection: 06.05.2012.

Faunal type: Mediterranean (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic.

151. 10449 *Bena bicolorana* (Fuessly, 1775)

Date of collection: 01.06.2008, 15.08.2008, 19.06.2009 and 23.06.2011.

Faunal type: Holomediterranean.

152. 10451 *Pseudoips prasinana* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Date of collection: 24.04.-16.08. (Appendix Table A-XLIV).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian.

153. 10444 *Nycteola asiatica* (Krulikovsky, 1904)

Date of collection: 08.07.-14.10 (Appendix Table A-XLV).

Faunal type: Boreo-continental.

154. 10456 *Earias clorana* (Linnaeus, 1761)

Date of collection: 20.04.-26.08. (Appendix Table A-XLVI).

Faunal type: Eurosiberian

155. 10459 *Earias vernana* (Fabricius, 1787)

Date of collection: 25.04.-27.08. (Appendix Table A-XLVII).

Faunal type: Boreo-continental

Analysis of data per family and subfamily is given in Table I.

Table I. Percentage of families and subfamilies in total number of captured specimens.

Family/Subfamily	Total species	Percentage of total species	Number of specimens	Percentage of total specimens
fam. Psychidae	1	0.34	1	0.0004
fam. Tortricidae	2	0.68	10	0.0045
fam. Cossidae	4	1.37	519	0.2320
fam. Limacodidae	1	0.34	7	0.0031
fam. Crambidae	3	1.03	178095	79.7827
fam. Drepanidae	4	1.37	143	0.0641
fam. Lasiocampidae	7	2.40	506	0.2267
fam. Saturniidae	1	0.34	15	0.0067
fam. Sphingidae	13	4.45	592	0.2652
fam. Geometridae	55	18.84	8953	4.0108
subfam. Ennominae	25	8.56	7896	3.5372
subfam. Geometrinae	1	0.34	6	0.0027
subfam. Larentiinae	16	5.48	268	0.1201
subfam. Sterrhinae	13	4.45	783	0.3508
fam. Notodontidae	14	4.79	433	0.1940
fam. Erebiidae	44	15.05	4423	1.9812
subfam. Lymantriinae	7	2.40	158	0.0708
subfam. Arctiinae	15	5.14	3665	1.6423
subfam. Herminiinae	2	0.68	13	0.0058
subfam. Hypeninae	2	0.68	90	0.0403
subfam. Rivulinae	1	0.34	347	0.1554
subfam. Scoliopteryginae	1	0.34	1	0.0004
subfam. Calpinae	1	0.34	9	0.0040
subfam. Aventiinae	1	0.34	13	0.0058
subfam. Eublemminae	2	0.68	30	0.0134

Family/Subfamily	Total species	Percentage of total species	Number of specimens	Percentage of total specimens (Table I – continued)
fam. Erebidae				
subfam. Phytometrinae	1	0.34	41	0.0184
subfam. Erebidae	11	3.77	133	0.0596
fam. Nolidae	6	2.05	531	0.2378
subfam. Nolinae	1	0.34	1	0.0004
subfam. Chloephorinae	5	1.71	530	0.2374
fam. Noctuidae	137	46.89	28921	12.9557
Total	292	100%	223,226	100%

Table II. Comparison of moth numbers in Čelarevo, conducted from 2008 to 2014 and Novi Sad, conducted from 1981 to 1991 (Kereši & Almaši, 2009).

Species	Total caught 179031	Rank by numerousness in Novi Sad	Total caught 223206	Rank by numerousness in Čelarevo
<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i>	36159	1	176366	1
<i>Tephрина arenacearia</i>	4261	3	3981	2
<i>Phragmatobia fuliginosa</i>	4575	2	2507	3
<i>Ascotis selenaria</i>	3387	5	1910	4
<i>Loxostege sticticalis</i>	3086	7	1728	5
<i>Timandra comae</i>	2167	8	574	6
<i>Chiasmia clathrata</i>	3517	4	526	7
<i>Phragmataecia castaneae</i>	804	10	464	8
<i>Spilosoma lubricipeda</i>	1751	9	350	9
<i>Rivula sericealis</i>	136	30	347	10
<i>Hyphantria cunea</i>	3242	6	124	21

Discussion

Ostrinia nubilalis is the most frequent species in Čelarevo. It accounts for 79.78% of all moths (Appendix Table A-V), with 176,366 specimens captured. In 2012, a record total of 50,407 specimens was registered, the highest number being 6398 moths per night (20th July).

The single specimen of *Cydalima perspectalis* was captured on 19th October, 2014. This Asian species was introduced to Europe in 2006. The first record for Serbia was in 2014 in Belgrade (Glavendekić, 2014, 2015).

Malacosoma neustria is mentioned as a potential pest in agricultural literature, but only one specimen was registered on 8th June, 2011.

Usually one to four specimens of *Agrius convolvuli* were registered per night. On 20th September 2011, 11 moths were registered per night. This was possibly due to migration.

We always registered one or two *Hyles livornica* moths per year in the light trap. From May 13th to 27th, 2009 we registered 30 moths! We suppose that this was a period of migration through Čelarevo. Moths were registered on 16th May. In the same period, nine moths were registered in Sombor in the light trap. This is the biggest number of this species since 1985 when the trap was set in Sombor.

Abraxas sylvata – a single specimen was registered on 22nd July, 2011.

Lomographa temerata – single specimen registered on 10th July, 2011.

Lycia hirtaria – single specimen registered on 8th April, 2010. This species usually flies in March and April, thus more frequent occurrence was expected in the area, since the collection started after the usual occurrence date.

Stegania cararia – nine specimens were registered on 23rd August, 3rd, 12th, 14th, 18th (2 specimens) and 22nd September, 2009, and 22nd July and 3rd August, 2011. In Serbia, the species is known only from Sombor, Valjevo, Kazan, Ledinci and Grgurevci (Vajgand, 1991, Zečević, 1987, Zečević 2002, Tomić *et al.*, 2002, and Stojanović *et al.*, 2010)

Cosmorhoe ocellata – single specimen registered on 24th August, 2011.

Colostygia pectinataria – single specimen registered on 25th May, 2011.

Cyclophora pendularia – single specimen registered on 8th June, 2009. In Serbia, found on Topčider hill (Belgrade), in Užice and Niš (Petterson, 1990 and Tomić *et al.*, 2002).

Rhodometra sacraria is a subtropical migrant species. We usually registered one moth per night, and one per year. In 2008 we registered 13 moths between 19th August and 15th October. Sometimes two moths were registered per night.

Scopula flaccidaria was registered in Serbia only in Sombor (Vajgand, 1995) and Božurovačka kosa (Tomić *et al.* 2002). We registered two moths in Čelarevo, on 12th August, 2008 and 19th September, 2012.

Hybocampa milhauseri – only one moth on 13th July, 2010. It is widespread but local, always individual and rare (Forster & Wohlfahrt, 1980).

Laelia coenosa – eleven moths registered. It is widespread, local in sandy places in Central Europe (Forster & Wohlfahrt, 1980). In Serbia it was registered only in Sombor (Vajgand, 1995), Pecka bara and Prahovo (Đerdap) (Zečević, 2002).

Thumatha senex – develops on moss and lichen. Nine samples collected. In Central Europe it is local in sandy meadows and forests (Forster & Wohlfahrt, 1980). In Serbia, in Sombor (Vajgand, 1995) and one moth in Petrovaradin (Stojanović, 2012). Abundance decreases with the drying of wet biotopes (Freina & Witt, 1987).

Dysauxes ancilla – only one moth registered on 7th July, 2013. It is widespread but local in Central Europe (Forster & Wohlfahrt, 1980).

Pelosia obtusa – very local and rare species in Central Europe (Forster & Wohlfahrt, 1980). Forty-two moths were collected in Čelarevo. From Serbia, the only data are from Novi Sad (Abafi, 1907) and Sombor (Vajgand, 2003).

Rhyparioides metelkana – single specimen registered on 15th July, 2011. This is a rare species of wetlands. In the region, only one specimen was known from Serbia, from Sombor (Vajgand, 1995), with a few from Hungary (Pecs and Com, Freyna & Witt, 1987). In Europe, it was registered in Romania (Danube delta) and in a few places in the southwest and north of France, southern Belgium, south of Berlin (Zossen) and southern Slovakia (Freyna & Witt, 1987).

Arytrura musculus – two specimens were caught on 28th June, 2008 and 7th July, 2009. This species has a disjunct areal in Europe and East Asia. Larvae feed only on *Salix cinerea* (Barany *et al.*, 2006). The species was registered in Romania between 1934-1939 in Capalnas near the Maros river and in the same place three decades later (König, 1975, König, 1978). Recent data are shown for the Danube delta (Latea, Periprava), southeastern Dobrudzha (Hagieni) and Moldova (Iasi, Botosani) Rákósy (1996). In Hungary, it was registered near Lake Balaton, 15 km north of the Drava river and between the Debrecen and Romanian border (South Nyirseg) (Barany *et al.*, 2006). There are no data for near the Danube River in Hungary.

With regards to faunal type, Eurosiberian (59.4%) and Holomediterranean (12.9%) species are predominant. It follows Boreo-continental (7.1%), Mediterranean- (Holomediterranean) western Asiatic (6.5%). Other faunal types have less than 2% share.

Between 72 and 109 species were registered annually. The smallest number of species was registered in 2014 and largest in 2011. The most specimens (52,849) were caught in 2012. In other years were registered less than 27,000 specimens. Smallest number of specimens was registered in 2010 (20,182).

A comparison has been made between the data from Novi Sad from 1981 to 1991 (Kereši & Almaši, 2009) and our data (Table II). The nine most common species are very similar in both places. *Hyphantria cunea* is much less present than in Novi Sad. The species *Rivula sericealis* takes 10th place in Čelarevo, being much more common than in Novi Sad, where it is 30th in place. A few species that are migrators were collected. In the group of Eumigrators are *Agrilus convolvuli* and *Acherontia atropos*. In the group of Emigrators (ditto) are: *Macroglossum stellatarum*, *Hyles livornica*, *H. euphorbiae*, *H. gallii*, *Nycteola asiatica*, *Grammodes stolidus*, *Orthonama obstipata*, *Rhodometra sacraria*, *Ostrinia nubilalis* and *Loxostege sticticalis*. A significant migration of *H. livornica* was registered in 2009.

Conclusions

The study of moths in Čelarevo was conducted from 2008 to 2014. A light trap, type RO Agrobečej, was used. Altogether, more than 234,000 moth specimens were collected, and 223,226 specimens were determined. A total of 292 moth species belonged to 14 families. Data are presented for 194,305 moths and 155 species (excluding Noctuidae family). Most common are moths of families Geometridae and Erebidae.

The most frequent species was *Ostrinia nubilalis* with 176,366 specimens or almost 80%, followed by *Tephrina arenacearia* (3981) and *Phragmatobia fuliginosa* (2507). This result is similar to that obtained by Kereši & Almaši (2009) for Novi Sad.

Most specimens were caught in 2012 (52,849) due to a massive occurrence of *Ostrinia nubilalis*. The greatest diversity was registered in 2011, with 109 species.

The Eurosiberian faunal type was the most common, with 92 species, or 59.4%.

Several rare or interesting species were caught: *Cydalima perspectalis*, *Stegania cararia*, *Cyclophora pendularia*, *Scopula flaccidaria*, *Laelia coenosa*, *Thumatha senex*, *Dysauxes ancilla*, *Pelosia obtusa*, *Rhyarioides metelkana* and *Arytrura musculus*.

A significant migration of *Hyles livornica* was registered.

Certain species recorded nearby were not recorded in this period at this location, and therefore our research will be continued.

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References

- Abafi Aigner, L. (1907). *Magyarország lepkéi*. Budapest, Hungary: Athenaeum irodalmi és nyomdai részvénytársulat kiadása, 137 pp.
- Baranyi, T., Józsa Á. CS. & Bertalan L. (2006). *Arytrura musculus* (Ménétriés, 1859). In Varga Z. (ed.) *Natura 2000 species studies kutatása I.* (pp 71-87). Debrecen, Hungary: Dél – Nyírség – Bikari Tájvédelmi és Kulturális Értkőrző Egyesület.
- Eitschberger U., Reinhardt R., Steiniger H. & Brehm G. (1991). Wanderfalter in Europa (Lepidoptera). *Atalanta* 22 (1), 18-67.
- De Freina, J. & Witt, T. (1987). *Die Bombyces and Sphinges der Westpaläarktis (Ins., Lepid.) Bd. 1.* München, Germany: Forschung & Wissenschaft Verlag GmbH, 708 pp.
- Forster, W. & Wohlfahrt Th. (1980). *Die Schmetterlinge Mitteleuropas Bd. 4.* Stuttgart, Germany: Franckh'sche Verlagshandlung, 329 pp.
- Forster, W. & Wohlfahrt Th. (1981). *Die Schmetterlinge Mitteleuropas Bd. 5.* Stuttgart, Germany: Franckh'sche Verlagshandlung, 312 pp.
- Forster, W. & Wohlfahrt Th. (1984). *Die Schmetterlinge Mitteleuropas Bd. 3.* Stuttgart, Germany: Franckh'sche Verlagshandlung, 239 pp.
- Glavendekić, M. (2014). The box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis* (Lepidoptera, Crambidae)-new pest in Serbia. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Book of abstract, VII Congress on plant protection, November 24-28, 2014* (pp. 267, 268). Zlatibor, Serbia: Plant protection Society of Serbia.
- Glavendekić, M. (2015). Šimširov plamenac-nove invazije sa mogućim katastrofalnim posledicama. In Anonymus (Ed.), *Zbornik predavanja Seminar pejasažna hortikultura 2014. Begrade 06.02.2015.* (pp. 31-35). Beograd, Srbija: Udruženje za pejasažnu hortikulturu Srbije i Univerzitet u Beogradu, Šumarski fakultet.

- Jakšić, P. & Dimović, D. (2000). The Review of the examined species of genera *Eilema* Hübner, 1819 and *Lithosia* Fabricius, 1798 in Bor town and surrounding area (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae, Lithosiinae). *Zaštita prirode* 52 (1): 47-63.
- Karsholt, O. & Nieuwerkerken, E.J. van. (2013). Lepidoptera, Moths. Fauna Europaea version 2.6.2. Retrieving from <http://www.faunaeur.org>
- Karsholt, O. & Razowski, J. (1996). *The Lepidoptera of Europe. A distributional Checklist*. Stenstrup, Danmark: Apollo Books, 380 pp.
- Kereši, T. & Almaši, R. (2009). Nocturnal Lepidoptera in the vicinity of Novi Sad (Northern Serbia). *Acta entomologica Serbica* 14 (2): 147-162.
- König, F. (1975). *Catalog of Lepidoptera collection in Banat's Museum*. Timisoara: Romania: Comitetul de cultura si educatie socialista Judetul Timis Muzeul Banatului Timisoara, 284 pp.
- Petterson, C. (1990). *Aletia languida* Walk, a moth new to Yugoslavia (Lep., Noctuidae) and other Lepidoptera species collected in Yugoslavia. *Acta entomologica Yugoslavica* 23 (1-2): 73-77.
- Rákósy, L. (1996). *Die Noctuiden Rumäniens*. Staphia 46. & Kataloge des O. Ö. Landesmuseums Neue Folge 105. Linz. Austria: Biologiezentrum Linz-Dornach. pp 648.
- Stojanović, D. (2012). *Taxonomic-faunistic study of butterflies and moths (Insecta: Lepidoptera) of Mt. Fruška gora* (Doctoral dissertation) University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology. Retrieving from: <http://www.doiserbia.nb.rs/phd/university.aspx?theseid=BG20121207STOJANOVIĆ#.VoFqo7bhCWg>
- Stojanović, D., Ćurčić, S. & Brajković, M. (2010). *The Geometrid moths (Lepidoptera, Geometridae) of mt. Fruška Gora (Norther, Serbia)*. Belgrade, Novi Sad and Podgorica. Serbia and Montenegro: Institut of Zoology, Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrad, Fruška gora National park, Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, University of Montenegro, 325 pp.
- Stojanović, D., Poljaković-Pajnik, L., Drekić, M. & Vajgand, D. (2006). New findings of species *zonaria* (Denis und Schiffermüller, 1775) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) for fauna of Serbia. In Anonymous (Ed.), *The book of abstracts and programme II International symposium of ecologists of the Republic of Montenegro 20-24.09.2006*. (pp 45,46). Podgorica & Kotor, Montenegro: Centre for Biodiversity of Montenegro, The republic Institution for the Protection of Nature, Natural History Museum of Montenegro, Institut for Marine Biology.
- Stojanović, D. & Vajgand, D. (2007). The Genus *Abrostola* Ochsenheimer, 1816 (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, Plusiinae) in Serbia and Montenegro. *Acta entomologica Serbica* 12 (1), 17-30
- Tomić, D., Zečević, M. & Glavendekić M. (2002). Fauna of Geometrids (Lepidoptera, Geometridae) in Serbia. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fauna of Serbia Vol VI*: 73-164. Belgrade, Serbia: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Department of Chemical and Biological Sciences.
- Vajgand, D. (1988). Familija sovcia u okolini Sombora, sa osvrtom na vreme javljanja u zavisnosti od ekoloških faktora. In M. Srbljanin & T. Balić-Žunić (Eds.), *Zbornik radova sinopsis, Peti jugoslavenski susret mladih istraživača "Nikola Tesla" Kumrovec 20-23. aprila 1988*. (pp. 98-100). Zagreb. Jugoslavija (Hrvatska): Narodna tehnika Hrvatske-Odbor za širenje znanstvenih saznanja "Nikola Tesla"
- Vajgand, D. (1995a). Contribution to the study of the Fauna of Lepidoptera of Serbia, unregistered species of butterflies in the Fauna of Serbia. *Matica Srpska Journal for Natural Sciences* 89: 29-36.
- Vajgand, D. (1995b). Stanje istraženosti faune noćnih leptira okoline Sombora. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik rezimea, XXII Skup entomologa Jugoslavije – Palić 5.-8. 09. 1995*. (pp 11). Beograd. Srbija: Entomološko društvo Srbije.
- Vajgand, D. (1995c). Prilog poznavanju faune leptira okoline Sombora – Bombyces i Sphinges. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik rezimea, XIX smotra naučnih radova studenata poljoprivrede – Novi Sad 17. novembar 1995*. (pp 17). Novi Sad, Srbija: Poljoprivredni fakultet.

- Vajgand, D. (1996). Fauna sovica (Noctuidae, Lepidoptera) u periodu 1992 – 1994. godina u području Sombora. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik rezimeza, Deseti jugoslavenski simpozijum o zaštiti bilja – Budva 30.09. – 04.10.1996.* (pp. 32, 33) Beograd, Srbija: Društvo za zaštitu bilja Srbije.
- Vajgand, D. (1999). Istraženost faune noćnih leptira (Lepidoptera) u Somboru do 1999. godine. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik rezimeza, Simpozijum entomologa Srbije '99. Goč, 21-23. oktobar 1999.* (pp 29). Beograd, Srbija: Entomološko društvo Srbije.
- Vajgand, D. (2001). Podaci o istraživanju faune noćnih leptira u Somboru tokom 1999. i 2000. godine. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik rezimeza, Simpozijum entomologa Srbije 2001. – Goč 26-29. septembar 2001.* (pp 27). Beograd, Srbija: Entomološko društvo Srbije.
- Vajgand, D. (2003). Podaci o istraživanju faune noćnih leptira i moljaca u okolini Sombora tokom 2001 i 2002 godine. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik plenarnih referata i rezimeza Simpozijum entomologa Srbije 2003. – Ivanjica 24-27. septembar 2003.* (pp 59). Beograd, Srbija: Entomološko društvo Srbije.
- Vajgand, D., Gavrilović, Z. & Jovanović Onć, E. (2009). Mass appearing *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner, 1808) during 2008 year and pest control. In R. Beskorovjani (Ed.), *Proceedings XXIII Conference of Agronomist, Veterinarians and technologists 15 (1-2): 85-91.* Belgrade, Serbia: Institut PKB Agroekonomik.
- Vajgand, D. (2009). Podaci o istraživanju noćnih leptira (Lepidoptera) u Bačkoj u periodu od 2003. do 2008. godine. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Plenarni referati i rezimei, Simpozijum entomologa Srbije 2009 sa međunarodnim učešćem, Soko Banja 23-27. septembar 2009.* (pp 50). Beograd, Srbija: Entomološko društvo Srbije.
- Vajgand, D. (2010a). *Priručnik o sovicama (Noctuidae, Lepidoptera) na svetlosnoj klopci.* Sombor. Srbija: Garden print.
- Vajgand, D. (2010b). Elementi prognoze pojave ekonomski značajnih leptira za lokalitet Čelarevo. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Zbornik rezimeza radova, X savetovanje o zaštiti bilja Zlatibor 29. novembar-3. decembar 2010.* (pp 130). Beograd, Srbija: Društvo za zaštitu bilja Srbije.
- Vajgand, D. (2010c). Flight dynamic of Lepidoptera of economic importance in Sombor during 2010 and forecast for 2011. *Acta entomologica Serbica 15(2): 205-219.*
- Vajgand, D. (2010d). Data on occurrence of economically significant moths for the locality Čelarevo (Vojvodina, Srbija). *Plant Doctor XXXVIII (6): 464-474.*
- Vajgand, D. (2011). Goath Moth Family (Cossidae, Lepidoptera) in Sombor (Vojvodina, Serbia) and forecast elements. In R. Beskorovjani (Ed.), *Proceedings of XXV Conference of Agronomist, Veterinarians and Technologists 2011.* 17(1-2): 149-155. Beograd, Srbija: Institut PKB Agroekonomik.
- Vajgand, D. (2012a). Occurrence of moth with potential economic significance in Bačka and Srem during 2011 and forecast for 2012. *Plant doctor XL (1): 6-21.*
- Vajgand, D. (2012b). *The Owlet Moths (Noctuidae, Lepidoptera) Fauna of Vojvodina and Parameters for Forecasting Abundance* (Doctoral dissertation). University in Novi Sad, Poljoprivredni fakultet.
- Vasić, K. (2002). Fauna of Noctuids (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in Serbia. In Anonymous (Ed.), *Proceedings of the fauna of Serbia VI:* 165-293. Belgrade, Serbia: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Department of Chemical and Biological Sciences.
- Zečević, M. (1987). New species of Macrolepidoptera in the Timok region (East Serbia). In Anonymous (Ed.), *Proceedings on the Fauna of SR Serbia IV* (pp 195-205). Beograd, Srbija: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, The Section for Natural and Mathematical Sciences.
- Zečević, M. (2002). *Leptiri Timočke krajine (Istočna Srbija).* Bor & Zaječar. Srbija: DŠIP Bakar Bor and Narodni muzej Zaječar, 307 pp.

ПРИЛОГ ПОЗНАВАЊУ LEPIDOPTERA ЧЕЛАРЕВА (ВОЈВОДИНА, СРБИЈА)

ДРАГАН ВАЈГАНД

Извод

Лептири су сакупљани светлосном клопком тип РО Агробечеј од 2008. до 2014. године у Челареву. Челарево се налази на левој обали Дунава, у квадрату УТМ са ознаком CR81. Као извор светлости је кориштена живина сијалица 250W у периоду од почетка априла до средине октобра. Прикупљено је 234.000 примерака. Одређено је 223.226 примерака. Они су сврстани у 292 врсте а оне припадају следећим породицама: Psychidae 1, Tortricidae 2, Cossidae 4, Limacodidae 1, Crambidae 3, Drepanidae 4, Lasiocampidae 7, Saturniidae 1, Sphingidae 13, Geometridae 55, Notodontidae 14, Erebidae 44 (Lymantriinae 7, Arctiinae 15, Herminiinae 2, Hypeninae 2, Rivulinae 1, Scoliopteryginae 1, Calpinae 1, Aveniinae 1, Eublemminae 2, Phytometrinae 1, Erebininae 11), Nolidae 6 и Noctuidae 137. У овом раду су приказани подаци о 194.305 примерака из 155 врста. Подаци о припадницима породице совица (Noctuidae) су у припреми. Значајан је налаз следећих врста:

- *Cydalima perpsectalis* - сакупљен један примерак 19. октобра 2014. године. У Србији је ово други налаз, за сада је забележена само у Београду;
- *Stegania cararia* - сакупљено је девет примерака. До сада је позната са свега пет места у Србији (Сомбор, Ваљево, Казан, Лединци и Гргуревци);
- *Cyclophora pendularia* - један примерак 8. јуна 2009. У Србији позната само са три локалитета (Топчидер, Ужице и Ниш);
- *Scopula flaccidaria* - забележена су два примерка 12. августа 2008. и 19. септембра 2012. До сада је забележена само на још два локалитета у Србији (Сомбор и Божуровачка коса);
- *Laelia coenosa* - забележено је једанаест примерака. У Србији је позната још само са три локалитета (Сомбор, Пецка бара и Прахово);
- *Thumata senex* - прикупљено је девет примерака. У Србији је позната само из Петроварадина;
- *Pelosia obtuse* - у Челареву је забележено 42 примерка. У Србији је позната из Сомбора и Новог Сада;
- *Rhyarioides metelkana* - је забележена само у једном примерку 15. јула 2011. године. У Србији је позната само из Сомбора. У Европи постоје подаци само за неколико подручја у Мађарској, Румунији, Француској, Белгији, Немачкој и Словачкој;
- *Arytrura musculus* - је током истраживања забележен са два примерка 28. јуна 2008. и 07. јула 2009. У Србији нема других налаза. У Европи присутна у Мађарској, Румунији, Украјини и Русији.

Appendix

Tabular data on numbers of collected individuals of selectes species, collected in Čelarevo between 2008 and 2014.

Table A-I. Collection data for *Cossus cossus* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	3	2	5	2	3	5	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	27
2009	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
2010	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
2011	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
2012	0	0	0	1	1	3	7	2	1	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	18
2013	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	2	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	11
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Total																			86

Table A-II. Collection data for *Z. pyrina* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	8
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
2012	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total																			40

Table A-III. Collection data for *P. castaneae* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ	
2008	0	1	1	14	12	7	8	10	4	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60
2009	0	0	7	5	8	2	3	5	16	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	48
2010	0	0	3	6	6	3	3	3	4	6	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	41
2011	0	0	5	10	9	3	5	4	10	5	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	55
2012	0	4	9	6	9	7	23	11	4	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	76
2013	0	0	8	11	2	4	9	6	9	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	54
2014	1	0	4	5	4	5	7	5	7	5	6	2	77	1	1	0	0	0	0	130
Total																			387	

Table A-IV. Collection data for *L. sticticalis* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ	
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	2	1	3	1	0	0	0	11
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	5	0	12
2012	0	0	0	199	33	2	80	60	273	26	8	97	220	14	11	1	0	0	1024
2013	1	1	1	0	0	0	3	404	171	3	4	3	4	6	2	0	0	0	603
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	20	35	0	0	11	6	1	0	0	0	75
Total																			1728

Table A-Va. Collection data for *O. nubilalis* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08
2008	0	0	3	159	584	258	145	97	94	736	1993
2009	0	0	8	405	951	1024	819	158	25	175	3490
2010	0	0	7	22	344	284	1011	38	17	254	1510
2011	0	0	4	341	1618	1618	232	82	47	843	3057
2012	0	0	3	45	103	425	247	80	165	7594	21591
2013	0	0	24	34	78	892	427	104	27	8	1692
2014	0	4	85	124	1207	798	699	127	41	415	3373

Table A-Vb. Collection data for *O. nubilalis* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	4133	1714	2778	8875	732	15	75
2009	9348	4514	2342	421	391	65	9
2010	5692	4085	868	348	2504	335	30
2011	5151	1082	1048	1182	455	122	28
2012	10147	1414	4560	2574	985	424	50
2013	10940	8284	383	445	503	216	35
2014	6170	2016	1532	3222	1054	182	23
Total							176366

Table A-VI. Collection data for *T. batiz* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	7
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	4
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	6	1	0	1	1	0	13
2011	0	6	0	0	0	1	1	4	7	1	1	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	26
2012	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	2	5	5	1	0	0	0	17
Total																			68

Table A-VII. Collection data for *H. pyritoides* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	8
2010	0	0	3	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	9	0	0	0	0	0	20
2011	0	0	2	6	5	0	3	1	0	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	24
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	4
Total																			56

Table A-VIII. Collection data for *L. quercus* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	3	0	0	0	0	0	7
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	7	3	0	0	0	0	12
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	7	4	1	0	0	0	18
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	3
Total																			44

Table A-IX. Collection data for *G. quercifolia* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	9	0	0	0	0	19
2009	0	0	0	1	4	1	0	0	0	0	1	3	18	20	6	4	0	0	58
2010	0	0	0	0	2	4	1	2	1	1	0	0	13	30	2	7	0	0	63
2011	0	0	0	0	3	10	2	11	4	8	0	1	16	13	9	2	1	0	80
2012	0	0	0	0	1	3	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	4	2	0	0	0	18
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	7
2014	0	0	0	0	3	1	1	0	1	0	1	5	13	22	10	6	1	0	64
Total																			309

Table A-X. Collection data for *O. pruni* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	12	3	2	1	2	0	0	0	25
2009	0	0	0	1	4	1	2	0	0	0	4	10	0	1	1	1	0	0	25
2010	0	0	0	0	1	4	7	0	0	1	0	12	7	4	0	0	0	0	36
2011	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	1	0	1	3	8	2	4	0	0	0	0	23
2012	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	0	3	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	19
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	7
2014	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	8
Total																			143

Table A-XI. Collection data for *M. tiliae* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	0	1	6	7	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	26
2009	0	5	1	4	2	0	2	0	0	2	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	22
2010	1	8	5	0	0	1	4	0	4	5	4	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	38
2011	0	6	2	0	1	4	0	1	3	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26
2012	0	4	1	0	1	1	1	0	2	3	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	17
2014	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total																			130

Table A-XII. Collection data for *S. ocellata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	8
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2010	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
2011	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
2012	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
2014	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Total																			27

Table A-XIII. Collection data for *L. populi* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	2	2	4	0	1	0	0	0	14
2009	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
2010	0	2	2	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	3	1	0	0	0	0	16
2011	0	1	1	3	2	2	0	1	2	5	2	4	3	0	2	0	0	0	28
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2014	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	3	2	0	0	0	12
Total																			79

Table A-XIV. Collection data for *A. convolvuli* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	6	6	2	8	2	0	0	25
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	2	9	10	1	1	0	27
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	4	11	11	4	16	3	4	56
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	3	1	4	11	2	14	1	40
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	0	6
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	6
Total																			165

Table A-XV. Collection data for *D. elpenor* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2010	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	6	9	2	4	2	0	0	0	0	27
2011	0	0	1	7	7	3	0	0	1	2	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	25
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	4
Total																			65

Table A-XVI. Collection data for *A. selenaria* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	26	15	22	4	53	170	27	2	0	0	0	322
2009	0	1	1	27	11	1	3	13	27	27	16	21	114	80	2	0	0	0	344
2010	0	1	7	3	7	2	5	8	19	51	24	27	280	158	1	1	0	0	594
2011	0	6	4	20	22	14	8	22	28	56	25	24	21	6	1	0	0	0	257
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	9	8	20	17	20	36	10	3	0	0	0	126
2013	0	1	10	3	0	1	0	1	6	11	6	4	12	17	1	0	0	0	73
2014	1	1	2	0	3	0	0	5	13	9	25	17	41	67	10	0	0	0	194
Total																			1910

Table A-XVII. Collection data for *E. atomaria* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	9	4	7	4	88	160	33	1	0	0	0	307
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	6	3	14	14	23	1	0	0	0	65
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	0	3	31	11	0	0	0	0	52
2011	0	1	0	0	0	0	5	11	9	32	5	45	141	113	1	0	0	0	363
2012	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	9	9	0	5	28	20	23	0	0	0	0	96
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	8
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	13	2	2	1	18	13	2	0	0	0	52
Total																			943

Table A-XVIII. Collection data for *L. marginata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
2009	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	7
2010	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	11
2011	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	12	17	5	10	2	6	2	0	0	0	0	58
2012	0	0	1	0	3	1	2	3	4	2	2	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	23
2013	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
2014	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	1	5	1	13	1	4	3	0	0	0	0	34
Total																			139

Table A-XIX. Collection data for *M. alternata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	6	4	1	1	7	10	3	0	0	0	0	35
2009	1	0	2	2	1	0	0	3	1	0	2	0	9	11	1	1	0	0	34
2010	0	0	6	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0	3	8	15	0	0	0	0	38
2011	1	2	1	3	3	6	3	12	20	13	2	3	8	12	1	0	0	0	90
2012	2	0	2	2	0	0	1	2	3	3	0	2	1	6	0	0	0	0	24
2013	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6	1	1	0	0	0	13
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	1	3	0	13	32	10	1	0	0	66
Total																			300

Table A-XX. Collection data for *C. clathrata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	0	2	5	0	2	10	4	4	1	0	0	33
2009	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	90	11	1	67	32	6	0	0	0	212
2010	0	3	0	0	0	1	6	1	1	10	1	5	102	38	1	8	0	0	177
2011	0	3	1	1	0	10	19	9	5	6	3	4	6	8	2	1	0	0	78
2012	0	3	0	0	0	2	5	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	1	0	0	15
2013	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2014	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	9
Total																			526

Table A-XXI. Collection data for *I. arenacearia* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	8	5	1	9	39	36	7	33	478	856	111	54	3	0	0	1640
2009	0	1	6	34	16	1	8	22	46	21	23	30	168	115	0	0	1	0	492
2010	0	1	5	2	7	0	0	8	38	20	8	145	100	29	0	1	2	0	366
2011	0	1	1	11	18	4	7	41	149	123	45	137	193	205	5	0	0	0	940
2012	2	6	10	4	6	3	5	6	15	17	2	112	101	73	1	3	0	0	366
2013	0	0	10	4	1	0	1	0	4	2	0	0	4	3	0	0	0	0	29
2014	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	8	7	19	33	42	31	4	1	0	0	148
Total																			3981

Table A-XXII. Collection data for *L. farinata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
2009	0	3	14	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30
2010	0	1	6	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
2011	0	1	2	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
2012	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
2013	0	4	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
2014	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Total																			76

Table A-XXIII. Collection data for *C. polygrammata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2009	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	7	6	0	20
2011	0	2	0	0	5	5	5	7	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	27
2012	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	10
2014	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	2	3	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	16
Total																			81

Table A-XXIV. Collection data for *I. muricata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	8	3	1	1	0	0	0	4	4	2	2	0	0	0	25
2009	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	8
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	4	3	0	0	0	0	10
2011	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	0	1	0	11
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	1	6
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Total																			64

Table A-XXV. Collection data for *I. aversata* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	3	1	3	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
2009	0	0	0	1	3	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	7
2010	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
2012	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	8
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
Total																			36

Table A-XXVI. Collection data for *R. vibicaria* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	4	1	4	0	2	0	0	0	1	17
2009	0	0	0	4	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	14
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
2012	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
2013	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2014	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
Total																			44

Table A-XXVII. Collection data for *T. comae* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	20	8	9	17	18	20	9	19	3	0	1	129
2009	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	6	9	11	1	4	21	21	8	3	0	88
2010	0	2	9	1	0	0	10	1	9	5	10	22	23	31	10	12	8	0	153
2011	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	0	3	2	2	1	0	0	0	14
2012	0	0	0	1	0	0	9	2	21	5	1	3	9	14	3	1	2	0	71
2013	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	5	4	1	8	8	12	1	1	48
2014	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	6	6	3	10	5	12	5	8	8	4	0	71
Total																			574

Table A-XXVIII. Collection data for *C. curtula* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
2009	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
2010	1	4	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	13
2011	1	5	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
2012	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4
2013	1	8	3	0	0	0	1	0	4	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	21
2014	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Total																			61

Table A-XXIX. Collection data for *C. anachoreta* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2011	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	4	10	0	0	0	7	1	0	0	0	25
Total																			31

Table A-XXX. Collection data for *Ph. tremula* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2009	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	7
2010	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	11
2011	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	4
2012	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	8
2013	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	8
2014	0	3	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	4	0	0	0	13
Total																			52

Table A-XXXI. Collection data for *P. palpina* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	2	0	4	7	1	0	2	3	3	4	2	0	0	0	28
2009	8	8	2	2	4	0	1	2	2	0	0	0	3	3	3	0	0	0	38
2010	7	1	8	0	3	2	2	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	1	1	0	0	30
2011	1	6	1	0	0	3	1	2	2	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	20
2012	1	4	1	0	1	4	5	2	2	3	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	27
2013	0	2	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	9
2014	0	4	0	1	2	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	14
Total																			166

Table A-XXXV. Collection data for *L. quadra* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
2009	0	0	0	0	0	7	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	2	5	2	0	10	0	0	28
2011	0	0	0	0	0	31	9	7	0	0	0	6	3	9	2	0	0	0	67
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total																			109

Table A-XXXVI. Collection data for *P. fuliginosa* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	1	6	37	111	42	14	16	27	94	60	22	7	0	0	437
2009	7	1	0	0	0	3	31	43	48	51	24	20	120	307	71	11	0	0	737
2010	1	7	3	0	0	0	53	56	120	30	12	42	168	140	16	17	6	1	672
2011	0	1	0	1	0	10	49	79	49	28	6	8	43	82	7	4	0	0	367
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	17	8	5	3	2	7	1	3	0	0	0	50
2013	0	1	0	6	2	4	0	0	3	3	0	1	2	9	4	1	3	0	39
2014	0	0	0	0	0	1	25	7	7	5	8	9	3	92	37	9	2	0	205
Total																			2584

Table A-XXXVII. Collection data for *S. lutea* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	3	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	9
2009	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	7
2010	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	5
2011	0	2	2	11	19	6	2	0	0	12	31	18	9	3	0	0	0	0	115
2012	0	1	4	1	6	3	4	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	23
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2014	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total																			161

Table A-XXXVIII. Collection data for *S. lubricipeda* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	1	2	1	3	1	0	1	2	1	7	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	26
2009	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
2010	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	6	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	24
2011	1	3	6	17	24	12	0	0	2	25	39	23	9	1	0	0	0	0	162
2012	0	0	7	12	7	3	0	1	12	35	17	8	1	1	0	0	0	0	104
2013	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	8
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	5	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	9
Total																			350

Table A-XXXIX. Collection data for *H. cunea* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	7
2009	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
2010	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	3	0	0	0	0	0	9
2011	0	0	0	12	8	3	1	0	0	11	13	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	59
2012	0	0	14	5	4	7	2	0	0	2	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	39
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
2014	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total																			124

Table A-XL. Collection data for *H. proboscidalis* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	5
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	0	0	0	4	7	7	1	0	27
2011	0	0	1	4	1	1	0	0	8	4	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	22
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	4	1	0	10
Total																			68

Table A-XLI. Collection data for *R. sericealis* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	5
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2010	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	5	4	2	1	12	4	3	6	0	0	41
2011	0	0	0	14	68	71	0	14	67	31	5	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	273
2012	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	3
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	5	1	1	1	7	2	1	0	1	21
Total																			347

Table A-XLII. Collection data for *C. salicalis* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	4	2	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	14
2009	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
2010	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	5
2011	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	8
2012	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2013	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	4
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	4
Total																			41

Table A-XLIII. Collection data for *D. algira* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ
2008	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	3	1	3	1	0	0	17
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	4	0	0	12
2010	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	5	5	2	7	2	0	26
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
2012	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	5	5	5	1	0	0	0	20
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	3
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	4
Total																			85

Table A-XLIV. Collection data for *P. prasinana* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ		
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
2009	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	
2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	
2011	0	5	0	4	1	0	0	0	1	10	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	
2012	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
																				Total	51

Table A-XLV. Collection data for *N. asiatica* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ		
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	4	1	0	0	0	11	
2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	3	0	1	1	0	0	9	
2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	12	7	3	1	1	15	0	40	
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	0	0	1	3	0	10	
																				Total	70

Table A-XLVI. Collection data for *E. clorana* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ		
2008	0	0	2	1	0	1	2	5	5	0	5	19	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	60	
2009	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	
2010	0	0	13	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	20	
2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	101	56	18	0	8	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	191	
2012	0	0	3	0	0	2	5	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	
2013	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	6	0	2	5	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	27	
																				Total	326

Table A-XLVII. Collection data for *E. vermana* in the period 2008-2014.

Dates	08-21.04	22.04-01.05	02-11.05	12-21.05	22-31.05	01-10.06	11-20.06	21-30.06	01-10.07	11-20.07	21-30.07	31.07-09.08	10-19.08	20-29.08	30.08-08.09	09-18.09	19-28.09	29.09-20.10	Σ	
2008	0	1	2	1	2	0	1	3	2	1	1	7	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	30
2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
2010	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
2011	0	2	0	1	0	2	8	4	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	22
2012	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
2013	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	6
2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	8
Total																			79	